

The International Society for Plant Pathology (ISPP) proposes a code of ethics for plant health emergencies*

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In August 2018, the Council of the International Society for Plant Pathology (ISPP), to which the Spanish Phytopathological Society (SEF) belongs, agreed to propose a code of ethics for plant health emergencies which was published in the ISPP Newsletter in December 2018. The code is now under public consultation which is why we decided to include a commented version of the code in the fourth issue of our SEF magazine, *Fitopatología* (Article published in Spanish). We remarked that some aspects may need to be considered further. This initiative of the ISPP follows other codes of ethics and conduct that are widely adopted by other scientific disciplines (EC 2013; WHO 2016). The code of ethics for plant health emergencies proposed by the ISPP has three main objectives:

- i) to foster ethical conduct;
- ii) to support communication and collaboration; and
- iii) to ensure that decisions are based on the best available evidence.

To achieve these goals, the code establishes five standards of practice:

1) Alert authorities and colleagues of new outbreaks

“Emergence of a new plant disease may be catastrophic if a rapid response is not taken by researchers, authorities or the relevant science organisation. It is a moral obligation of researchers and professional associations to alert the gravity of the emergency to the authorities and other stakeholders. Sharing available information with local and international colleagues may lead to the engagement of a higher number of experts to rapidly tackle the emergency. Social networks such as Twitter, Facebook and an open data sharing internet platforms are useful for on-time sharing of real information, exchange of views and to connect researchers. Engaging relevant stakeholders would expedite development of appropriate strategies and approaches to rapidly mitigate the problem.” – ISPP 2018

In this regard, it is important to note that the EU plant health law (EU Regulation 2016/2031) clearly establishes in article 15 a mandatory obligation for any citizen to immediately notify the relevant plant health authority of the presence, or suspected presence, of a quarantine pest within EU territory. Likewise, the plant health law in Spain (Ley 43/2002) establishes in article 5 the obligation to notify the relevant authorities of the Autonomous Communities or the Central Government of any atypical appearance of symptoms or organisms harmful to plants.

As a scientific society, the SEF publishes reports of new plant pathogens described in Spain in its magazine *Fitopatología*. We also maintain a catalogue of plant pathogens in coordination with the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA) which is the National Plant Protection Organization (NPPO) in Spain. Furthermore, the books of abstracts of the SEF congresses are sent to the Ministry prior to publication, which means that the National Plant Protection Organization is the first to be informed of any new detection of plant pathogens that will be presented in our meetings. In addition, the SEF has a group of experts specialized in the detection and identification of plant pathogens microorganisms, and the diagnosis of plant diseases (GEDDI-SEF).

2) Honestly and accurately report information

“Ethical scholarly communications or research conduct implies practice of fundamental ethical principles in scientific research. In any plant health emergency, researchers must be critical, honest, transparent and highly responsible for sharing information and research data. The Code of Ethics ensures the highest standard in research and scholarly communications. It safeguards the standard behaviour and practices of the researchers. To the best of their ability, plant health researchers must follow universally acceptable and interdisciplinary code of conducts in sharing and exchanging any information or data. Open science and open data sharing approaches allow transparency and criticisms by peers.” – ISPP 2018

It is crucial to stress the importance of the quality and the reliability of the information that is passed to the competent plant health authorities and interest groups. This relates to both this point and the previous one about new disease reports. The communication of partial or inconclusive results would eventually lead to false alarms which may result in unjustified phytosanitary actions, negatively affecting the credibility of the whole system. Scientific societies like SEF play a key role in providing the public and authorities with sound information, based on scientific evidence and verified by specialists on the topic.

3) Openly share biomaterial and data

“To rapidly mitigate any emergent plant health issue in any region of the world, an open data sharing approach is critical for engaging the global scientific community and securing required funding for needed research. The data sharing enables genetic identification and diagnostics, and sets the stage for surveillance, epidemiology and rapid response. These approaches would engage the greater global scientific community to address a local serious plant health problem for a rapid solution. Researchers of plant health emergencies should take necessary steps for sharing biomaterial and data with the local and global scientific communities to allow a concerted effort to tackle the problem.” – ISPP 2018

Open-data policies are becoming the standard in many scientific disciplines, driven by the individual initiatives of researchers or owing to the requirements of scientific journals and funding agencies. The programme Horizon 2020 of the European Commission launched the ‘open access to research data’ pilot, with the aim of enhancing the access and use of data from EU-funded research. From this pilot, the European Commission recognized the legal constraints to openly share particular types of data and currently applies the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’ (EC 2017). The cOAlition S initiative, formed by the main funding bodies in Europe,

also follows the same principle (SE 2019). As E.M. Del Ponte, A.H. Sparks and E. González-Domínguez point out in the SEF's fourth issue of *Fitopatología*, the adoption of open-data practices in our discipline are far from optimal, and so, they propose specific measures to make progress with this.

In relation to sharing biomaterial, it is important to also consider the issues about biosecurity. The EU plant health law ([EU Regulation 2016/2031](#)) establishes the conditions and procedures for the introduction and movement of quarantine pests and certain plant species for scientific or educational purposes, official testing, trials, varietal selection and breeding. An official authorisation needs to be granted, and the activity has to be carried out in a designated quarantine station or confinement facility, with personnel having appropriate scientific and technical competence. In relation to this, the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (EPPO) published a guideline describing the confinement conditions in laboratory and glasshouse for organisms classified as requiring biosecurity levels (EPPO 2006). All these regulations and recommendations are aimed to reduce the risk of inadvertent introductions of regulated pathogens in natural and agricultural settings when imported for research purposes. Nevertheless, the potential risks associated with the movement of non-regulated pathogens in the form of exotic strains, races or pathotypes should also be considered when sharing biomaterial.

In the same way that digital repositories such as Zenodo and sequence databases such as GenBank are key for open-data policies, public culture collections also play a fundamental role as repositories and providers of biomaterials. During the XIX SEF congress our specialized group in diagnosis, detection and identification organized a symposium together with the Spanish Type Culture Collection (CECT) as the reference Microbial Biological Resource Centre (mBRC) in Spain to support this goal. After the detection of a new pathogen in an area, the deposit of representative strains in public culture collections would allow us to follow the ISPP code of ethics while complying with the biosecurity requirements for biomaterial preservation and distribution. However, as pointed out at the GEDDI-SEF symposium, deposits in culture collections have certain limitations in the case of nematodes, viruses, obligate parasites and other non-cultivable organisms, since many of them are not supported by standard conservation methods.

4) Collaborate with experts on the problem

“Engagement or collaboration with the leading experts in any specific plant health related problem is critical for a rapid solution. Plant health related local and international professional organisations should take immediate steps to engage the right experts through organising seminar, symposia, workshop or conference. Collaboration in research with high level experts saves time and resources for the mitigation of any problem in plant health science.” – ISPP 2018

For many years, the SEF developed several activities to engage with international experts on different plant diseases, so that they can contribute with their experiences to prevent and manage plant health emergencies in our country. For instance, when selecting the international speakers invited to our national SEF congresses, the organizing committees always consider which actual or potential plant health threats are present at that time.

5) Respect and acknowledge the work of other scientists

“It is the responsibility of the researchers to equally consider the ideas of all those who engage with the problem, and acknowledge contributions of any researcher from anywhere. Supporting diversity is crucial for greater scientific outcomes and acceptance of the research-based solution by society as a whole. Another ethical issue is trusting and empowering less experienced researchers and help them to achieve their professional goals and realise their full potential.” – ISPP 2018

References

EC, European Commission (2013). “Ethics for researchers. Facilitating research excellence in FP7”. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation; Science in society/Capacities FP7, 36 pp.

EC, European Commission (2017). “H2020 Programme. Guidelines to the rules on open access to scientific publications and open access to research data in Horizon 2020”. Version 3.2, 11 pp.

EPPO, European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (2006). “Intentional import of organisms that are plant pests or potential plant pests”. Phytosanitary procedures PM 3/64 (1). *Bulletin OEPP/EPPO Bulletin* **36**: 191-194.

ISPP, International Society of Plant Pathology (2018). “Call from ISPP: A code of ethics for plant health emergencies”. *ISPP Newsletter* **48**: 3-4.

SE, Science Europe (2019). “cOAlition S: Accelerating the transition to full and immediate open access to scientific publication”. Coordinated by Science Europe, AISBL, 9 pp.

WHO, World Health Organization (2016). “Policy statement on data sharing by the World Health Organization in the context of public health emergencies”. WHO, support for IHR monitoring implementation, key document, 4 pp.